

Notes

Formation Constants of Tartronic Acid Complexes with Metal Ions

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THE present paper deals with the *pH* metric studies of Tartronic acid complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , which have been carried out to establish the composition of these complexes, and also to determine their stability constants. Metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by Irving-Rossotti¹ technique. All the experiments were performed at 27°, and constant ionic strength of 0.1*M*, 0.2*M* and 0.3*M* NaClO_4 .

Experimental

Calculated amount of tartronic acid (Fluka AG) was dissolved in double distilled water to give 0.01*M* solution.

The solutions of the metal ions were made from B. D. H. AnalaR grade chemicals and were standardised against EDTA².

For *pH* metric titrations, the metal ion solutions (0.005*M*) were made in perchloric acid, the strength of the acid being determined titrimetrically³.

Sodium-perchlorate (E. Merck) was employed for maintaining constant ionic strength. A mains operated Philipps *pH* meter, which has a least count of 0.05 *pH* unit was employed for *pH* measurements.

Determination of stability constants: In the present case the formation constants have been obtained by the analysis of formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} against *pL*. From the values of \bar{n} and *pL*, the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been calculated as usual by various experimental and computational methods⁴. Tartronic acid has two replaceable hydrogens and hence *Y* has been considered two. The values of the protonation constants of the ligand has been calculated as usual by the plot of $\bar{n}A$ against *pH*.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF TARTRONIC ACID AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ITS COMPLEXES, TEMP := 27°

System	Constants	$\mu = 0.1M$	$\mu = 0.2M$	$\mu = 0.3M$
H^+ -Tartronic Acid	$\log \beta^H$	9.10	9.05	8.40
Cu(II)-TA	$\log K_1$	11.70	10.30	7.60
	$\log K_2$	2.80	2.50	1.00
	$\log \beta$	14.50	12.80	8.60
Ni(II)-TA	$\log K_1$	8.30	6.60	6.40
	$\log K_2$	2.50	2.30	2.10
	$\log \beta$	10.80	9.60	8.50
Mn(II)-TA	$\log K_1$	6.50	6.10	4.95
	$\log K_2$	3.45	1.10	1.05
	$\log \beta$	9.95	7.20	6.00

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Table 1 gives the values of the overall proton-ligand stability constant and the stepwise metal-ligand stability constants.

From the table, it is seen that the stability constants of divalent metal ions at the various ionic strengths obey Irving-Williams⁵ order,

The value of stability constants of transition metal ions, increases according to the atomic number.

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Coordination Compounds of Diarylthio Dihalides with Diethyl Amine

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DIETHYLAMINE has been used as a Lewis base and complexes with transition and non-transition metals have been reported¹⁻³. The corresponding molecular adducts of organotin have not so far been investigated and it was considered of interest to synthesise complexes of this Lewis base with various diarylthio dihalides and to examine their structure.

Experimental

The complexes were obtained by the direct interaction of the Lewis acids with diethyl amine in a suitable solvent using conventional ground glass apparatus. Manipulations were carried out in a dry box flushed with nitrogen.

The conductance measurements of representative complexes were made by Philipps, magic eye, conductivity bridge model PR 9500 and the molecular weights were

determined cryoscopically using Beckmann thermometer of accuracy 0.01° . The infrared spectra in nujol were recorded in the range $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer.

Materials: The Lewis acids employed in this investigation were prepared according to the reported methods⁴. Diethyl amine (BDH) was used.

Preparation of the complexes: Excess of a solution of the amine in diethyl ether was added to about 2 m mole of diaryl tin dihalide in the same solvent. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed several times with the same solvent and dried in vacuum. The experimental results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2Et_2NH$

R	X	m.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	analysis %		Found (Calc.)	
			Sn	C	H	N
phenyl	Cl	162	24.10 (24.28)	48.52 (48.93)	6.25 (6.53)	5.51 (5.72)
			o-tolyl	Cl	196	22.62 (22.97)
Br	224	19.19 (19.60)				43.12 (43.49)
		I	184	16.51 (17.00)	37.27 (37.72)	5.19 (5.14)
m-tolyl	Cl			176	22.55 (22.97)	50.56 (50.96)
		p-tolyl	Cl		180	22.43 (22.97)
Br	194			19.21 (19.60)		43.32 (43.49)
		I	191	17.12 (17.00)	37.26 (37.72)	5.22 (5.14)

The complexes possess 1 : 2 stoichiometry. They are white crystalline solids, thermally stable with sharp melting points and are soluble in nitrobenzene.

The molar conductances of 10^{-3} M solution of the complexes in nitrobenzene, observed below $5\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mole}^{-1}$, indicate absence of ionic species. However experimentally determined molecular weight of some of the complexes is considerably lower than the formula weight indicating significant decomposition of the complexes in solution.

Infrared spectra: A comparison of the spectra of the complexes with that of the free base indicates distinct lowering of the N-H stretching frequency from 3335 cm^{-1} to $3190 \pm 30\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The asymmetric and symmetric $\nu\text{C-N}$ identified at 1148 and 890 cm^{-1} respectively in the spectrum of diethyl amine also undergo negative shift to the extent of 108 ± 5 and $65 \pm 35\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The changes indicate the presence of co-ordinated base. In the far IR region, the identification of two new absorptions at 427 ± 13 and $364 \pm 12\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of the complexes are attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn-N})$ stretching vibration, which is a direct evidence for coordination

from the nitrogen atom of the base^{6,7}. Three other distinct absorptions occurring at 286 ± 9 , 257 ± 8 and 248 ± 6 are assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{Sn-Cl})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{Sn-Cl})$ respectively.⁸⁻⁹ $\nu(\text{Sn-Br})$ and $\nu(\text{Sn-I})$ are expected to lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

The analytical, infrared, and conductivity data indicate hexa co-ordinated octahedral compounds.

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Alkali Metal Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with Bidentate Chelating Diol

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SIDGWICK and Brewer¹ first reported that hydrated salts of sodium benzoylacetone was soluble in toluene and benzene, had a sharp melting point and lost water above 115° . Similar observations were also recorded by them about the dihydrates of lithium methyl salicylate (Li. MS), lithium salicylaldehyde and sodium acetylacetonate. Nyholm and others² also recorded that anhydrous red potassium-*o*-nitrophenolate (K. ONP) changed to orange monohydrate on exposure to atmosphere. That the above mentioned compounds were coordinated complexes was based on a) solubility

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